

FATIGUE DAMAGE DEVELOPMENT IN CARBON FIBER REINFORCED EPOXY COMPOSITES:
CORRELATION BETWEEN THE STIFFNESS DEGRADATION AND THE GROWTH OF
DIFFERENT DAMAGE TYPES

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INTRODUCTION

Fatigue loading of a carbon fiber reinforced epoxy composite laminate can result in a degradation of the stiffness properties of the laminate. This stiffness reduction is due to the initiation, growth and interaction of different damage types in the laminate. Matrix cracking, delamination between the plies, debonding and fiber fracture are the damage modes which are known to occur during tension-tension fatigue loading of carbon fiber reinforced epoxy laminates. Each of these damage modes has his own potential of reducing the stiffness of the laminate, but the interaction between the different damage modes plays also a major part in this degradation process.

This paper discusses the correlation between the stiffness reduction during tension-tension fatigue of $(O_2, 90_2)_s$ laminates made of Fiberdux 920C-TS-5-42 prepreg of Ciba Geigy and the growth of the damage modes during fatigue.

STATE OF THE ART

Acoustic emission (AE) has been used by several authors as a means to monitor microdamage development during fatigue testing of composites in a continuous, passive (this means: non interactive) way. A set of recent papers on AE can be found in (1).

In previous papers (2,3) we have presented a new method of analyzing AE-data. The energy content of the AE-events has been correlated to different damage modes, using other nondestructive test techniques as calibration tools. Low energy events can be correlated to matrix cracks, medium energy events to delaminations and high energy events to fiber fracture. However, careful quantitative examination revealed that AE-events do not always have to be generated during crack extension, but also during crack closure, which involves also specific damage mechanisms.

LONGITUDINAL STIFFNESS DEGRADATION and HYSTERESIS measurements are carried out to confirm our findings obtained with the AE-measurements and thus to underline the crack closure concept.

MECHANICAL TESTING

The fatigue tests are carried out on a servohydraulic fatigue testing machine (Schenck Hydropuls, 25kN). The $(0_2, 90_2)_s$ laminate is tested up to $\sigma_{max} = 0,7 \sigma_{UTS}$, which means $\sigma_{max} = 548$ MPa. The frequency is 3Hz, the cycle sinusoidal. For the same maximum stress, two different test series are carried out on this laminate type: one with $R = 0.03$ and another series with $R = 0.5$. The former tests are carried out for 280000 cycles and the latter for 500000 cycles.

DAMAGE MONITORING

- Three different nondestructive test techniques are used to monitor the damage initiation and development. These techniques are described elsewhere (2,3) and will be mentioned only briefly in this paper. Acoustic emission (AE) is used for continuous and passive monitoring. The AET 5000 A apparatus allows us to carry out full analysis of the AE-events. In this study, we focus on energy distribution of AE-events, the stress level at which the AE-events are generated, and the number of AE-events vs. the number of cycles. At regular intervals, replica's are taken of the edges of the specimen. They are investigated under the light microscope, so that maps of matrix cracks and delaminations can be drawn at intermediate numbers of cycles, and at the end of each test.

X-ray radiographs are taken at the end of each test in order to visualize the internal damage state of the specimen. ZnI_2 is used as an enhancing agent. It is penetrated under a low strain.

- The longitudinal stiffness degradation measurements are carried out using a dynamic extensometer, Instron 2620-602, with a gauge length of 100mm.

RESULTS

Damage information from the penetrant enhanced X-ray radiographs and replicas.

On figure 1 the photograph of the penetrant enhanced X-ray radiographs of test 1 ($R=0.03$) taken after 280000 cycles is pictured. In figure 2 these of test 3 ($R=0.5$) after about 500000 cycles is shown. The following information is deduced from these radiographs.

- nearly equal damage states for both specimens tested at $R=0.03$ is reached, whilst the fatigue damage state for the specimen tested at $R=0.5$ is less severe.
- some matrix cracks indicated on the radiographs of tests 1 and 2 are revealed whereas the specimen of test 3 do not show any evidence of this feature.

We quantify the matrix cracks present in the specimens by calculating for each radiograph the number of matrix cracks and also the total length of the matrix cracks. For the number of matrix cracks we make a distinction between the matrix cracks formed on the edge of the specimen, where the replicas are taken (front), and the other edge (back), where during the course of the test no replica is taken. This in order to find a possible influence of acetone on the fatigue damage development used to weaken the replicas before they are placed on the edge.

Radiograph of test:		# of matrix cracks	
		front	back
R=0.03	280000 cycles	69	68
	280000 cycles	69	59
R=0.05	507150 cycles	44	32

Radiograph of test:		total length of matrix cracks in real mm
R=0.03	280000 cycles	570 mm
	280000 cycles	477 mm
R=0.5	507150 cycles	165 mm

These values indicate that the tests of the series with R=0.03 have almost the same number and length of matrix cracks whereas the tests of the series with R=0.5 have a clearly smaller number of matrix cracks; their total length is only one third of the length of the cracks in the R=0.5 test.

All specimens have a smaller number of matrix cracks starting from the back edge of the specimen, indicating a possible influence of acetone on the damage development. This is a drawback of the replication technique if often replicas have to be taken.

In figures 3 and 4 the history of the fatigue damage development on the edges as revealed by the replicas is depicted, respectively for tests 2 and 3. In figure 3 (test 2) we notice that no additional full thickness cracks can be found after about 75000 fatigue cycles. More small matrix cracks, frequently at an angle to the other matrix cracks, are formed hereafter. Incipient delaminations are already formed after 15000 fatigue cycles and grow along the interface between the 0° and 90° plies. The final damage state reached after 280000 fatigue cycles for tests 1 and 2 is comparable. For test 3 the damage state as can be seen on the last replica taken after 507150 fatigue cycles is much less severe than for tests 1 and 2: less full thickness matrix cracks and only very small incipient delaminations.

The information of the delamination damage on the replicas taken when the fatigue test is stopped, is quantified in the following way. We count the number of full thickness matrix cracks over the full length of the replica and also the total length of incipient delaminations over a part of the length of the replica.

Replica of test	# of matrix cracks	the total length of incipient delaminations (in mm)
R=0.03		
1 280000 cycles	43	394
2 280000 cycles	54	330
3 507150 cycles	36	53

Based on these values we can once more conclude that the fatigue damage state after 280000 fatigue cycles of the specimens tested at R=0.03 is the same. For the test at R=0.5 a fatigue damage state is obtained which is much less severe: as far as the incipient delaminations are concerned the damage state is definitely less.

Fatigue damage development monitored by the acoustic emission technique.

The results of the AE-measurements will be discussed on the basis of the total number of acoustic emission signals measured during each fatigue test and based on the fatigue damage growth curves. For the Energy Discriminating Acoustic Emission Method (EDAEM), the same energy interval allotment for the specific fatigue damage modes is used as for fatigue tests on $(0^{\circ}_2, 90^{\circ}_2)_s$ laminates: matrix cracking [28,51], delamination [52,78], debonding [79,98] and fibre fractures [99,111].

The plots of the total number of acoustic emission signals versus fatigue cycles for tests 1,2 and 3 (figure 7) show a clear difference: not only the total number of AE-events at the end of test 3, R=0.5, is much smaller than for the R=0.03 tests 1 and 2, but the final slope of the former curve is 7 times smaller than the slope of the latter. This means that the rate of the acoustic emission activity of test 3 is much smaller than the rates obtained for tests 1 and 2; only up to about 75000 fatigue cycles the rates are similar. This correlates well with

the moment revealed by the replicas of tests 1 and 2, from which on full thickness matrix cracks are no longer found to be formed. The growth curves of the fatigue damage modes of each fatigue specimen are correlated with the information on the fatigue damage we already have. From the growth curves (as in figure 6 for $R=0.03$ and fig. 7 for $R=0.5$) the number of AE-events for matrix cracking and delamination by the end of each fatigue test can be derived:

		max # AE-events for matrix cracking	max # AE-events for delamination
R = 0.03	Test 1	2299	2063
	Test 2	1928	1738
R = 0.5	Test 3	1011	643

These values are compared with the other most reliable quantitative values we have on the fatigue damage modes:

		The total length of the matrix cracks on the radiographs	The total length of incipient delaminations in mm on a small part of the last replica
enlarged R=0.03	test 1	570	394
	test 2	477	330
R=0.5	test 3	165	53

When we divide the corresponding # AE-events of the fatigue damage mode mentioned above by these total lengths the following factors are obtained:

R=0.03	test 1	4.03	5.24
	test 2	4.04	5.27
R=0.5	test 3	6.12	12.13

These results indicate the quantitative possibilities of the acoustic emission method: for the tests of the first series the same factors are

obtained indicating the direct correlation between the extent of a specific fatigue damage and the number of acoustic emission signals generated by the development and growth of that damage mode. For the test of the second series, a smaller extent of the fatigue damage modes correlate with less acoustic emission signals measured, but the factors obtained are slightly higher.

Fatigue damage development monitored with the longitudinal stiffness degradation method

A typical stiffness degradation curve for test 1 at $R=0.03$ is given in figure 8 and for the test at $R = 0.5$ in figure 9. The hysteresis curves (closed loop $\sigma-\epsilon$ curves) for several fatigue cycles of tests at $R=0.03$ and $R=0.5$ are given resp. in figures 10 and 11. From the stiffness degradation curves the following can be deduced:

- for the fatigue tests at $R=0.03$ the stiffness degradation as revealed on the log scale starts at 24000 fatigue cycles for test 1 and at 27000 for test 2.
- for the fatigue test at $R=0.5$ the stiffness degradation starts only after 90000 fatigue cycles and is much smaller.

The hysteresis curves reveal additional information on the fatigue damage development. For the curves for test 1, figure 10, one can see that the upper part of the $\sigma-\epsilon$ curves shifts parallel to itself but the lower part becomes convex towards the end of the fatigue test. For the curves of test 3, figure 11, only a parallel shift of the whole curve is measured.

From studies in metals it is well known that the stress-strain curve has a convex shape, if a mismatch between the crack surfaces is created during the crack extension proces. This phenomenon is called "crack closure", which means that the two opposing crack surfaces contact each other at a positive stress, before reaching the minimum of the sinusoidal stress function. The evidence of crack closure for the tests 1 and 2 is also measured by recording the value of the dynamic force at the occurrence of the acoustic emission signals generated by the fatigue damage modes (not very accurate however due to the bad sampling rate). On figure 12a for test 1 one can notice the high

acoustic emission activity at low stress levels which is not so pronounced for test 3 of the second series, figure 12b.

Micromechanics of damage development in (0₂,90₂) laminates: the concept of crack closure

The micromechanics of the formation of straight, full thickness matrix cracks are well described in literature (4). The formation of small matrix cracks, at a $\pm 45^\circ$ angle to the full thickness matrix cracks, and the formation of microdelaminations along these cracks, are reported in literature as well, but their existence has not been fully explained. In our opinion, the concept of "crack closure" provides a sound explanation.

During the growth of 90°-cracks, material debris is formed between the crack faces. This excess material causes compressive forces in the 90°-layer. As the shear strength is low, matrix cracks parallel with the plane of maximum shear stress can be formed. It can be shown that for a similar reason, small delaminations will be formed along these 90° cracks.

These additional damage modes, formed during the lower part of the sinusoidal load function, will cause additional acoustic emission at low load levels, as can be seen in fig. 12a. When these low load levels are not present, namely in test 3 at R=0.5, no increased AE-activity can be observed at the minimum load (fig. 12b). This observation is in agreement with the edge replica image (fig. 4), where only very few microdelaminations are present after 507150 fatigue cycles, possibly caused by stress concentrations at the tip of the 90°-cracks at the interface between the 0° and 90° plies at the edges.

CONCLUSIONS

The research described in this paper proves the quantitative possibilities of the Energy Discriminating Acoustic Emission Method and the damage growth curves for each distinct damage type based on this method.

The AE-method gives the same information as the longitudinal stiffness degradation method as far as the total number of acoustic emissions is concerned. However, it gives more information on the development of specific fatigue damage modes. In carrying out this research towards the quantitative possibilities of the acoustic emission technique, more information on the micromechanisms of the different fatigue damage modes is obtained. The importance of crack closure in the development of fatigue damage is discovered.

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Fig. 1: Penetrant enhanced X-ray radiograph for the first fatigue test on $(0_2, 90_2)_S$ laminate ($R=0.03$) (280000 cycles)

Fig. 2: Penetrant enhanced X-ray radiograph for the third fatigue test on $(0_2, 90_2)_S$ laminate ($R=0.5$) (500000 cycles)

Fig. 3: Damage history on the replica's of the second fatigue test on $(0_2, 90_2)_s$ laminate ($R=0.03$)

Fig. 4: Damage history on the replicas of the third fatigue test on $(0_2, 90_2)_s$ laminate ($R=0.5$)

Fig. 5: Cumulative plot of the total number of the AE-events versus the number of fatigue cycles for tests at $R=0.03$ and $R=0.5$

Fig. 6: Growth curves of the fatigue damage modes for test 1 ($R=0.03$)

Fig. 7: Growth curves of the fatigue damage modes for test 3 (R=0.5)

Fig. 8: Stiffness degradation curve for test 1 (R=0.03)

Fig. 9: Stiffness degradation curve for test 3 (R=0.5)

Fig. 10: Hysteresis curves for test 1 after some fatigue cycles (R=0.03)

Fig. 11: Hysteresis curves for test 3 after some fatigue cycles ($R=0.5$)

Fig. 12: Distribution graph of the value of the dynamic force at the occurrence of an acoustic emission signal

- a. at $R = 0.03$ (test 1)
- b. at $R = 0.5$ (test 2)